

Navigating the Challenges of AI-Generated Image Detection in the Wild: What Truly Matters?

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Abstract

As generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) advances, the realism of AI generated imagery has reached a threshold capable of deceiving even vigilant human observers. Yet, while current AI-generated Image Detection (AID) approaches perform exceptionally well on controlled benchmark datasets, they struggle significantly with real-world cases. To study this behavior we introduce the **ITW-SM** dataset, a curated collection of real and AI-generated images originating from major social media platforms. We employ it to analyze the effects of key design choices typically considered when building a detector, involving its architecture, pre-trained latent spaces, training data as well as pre-processing approaches. We indicate that naively scaling the pre-training stage or opting for more training data does not always lead to better detection performance. Instead, our work reveals that it is crucial to optimize each design choice to enable the processing pipeline to propagate and effectively analyze both low-level traces as well as high-level image semantics. Building on our findings, we achieve a substantial average improvement of 26.87% in AUC across multiple state-of-the-art detection approaches and under real-world conditions, providing a roadmap for developing more resilient detectors. Our assets are available on <https://mever-team.github.io/itw-sm>.

CCS Concepts

• **Computing methodologies** → *Image representations; Supervised learning by classification; Neural networks*; • **Applied computing** → **Evidence collection, storage and analysis**; • **Security and privacy** → **Social network security and privacy**.

Keywords

ai-generated image detection, deepfake detection, image forensics, media forensics

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1 Introduction

Generative AI has revolutionized digital media, enabling the creation of photorealistic content on demand via natural language descriptions [35]. While such tools offer immense creative potential, they also pose significant risks, as they can be maliciously exploited to spread disinformation, facilitate impersonation, or enable fraudulent activities [55]. Because their high fidelity deceives even careful human observers [38, 44], and the sheer volume of online media prevents manual review, robust automated AI-generated Image Detection (AID) deployed in the wild is crucial.

Existing AID approaches span pixel-level methods operating on raw image data [9, 15, 20, 56], fingerprint-based methods targeting frequency domain or reconstruction artifacts [2, 17, 26, 36], and zero-shot approaches for generalized, training-free detection [12, 22]. Despite the growing number of AID methods, achieving robust performance in real-world scenarios remains a challenge, as most AID models perform exceptionally well on benchmark datasets [48], which are typically generated in controlled environments, but collapse when unconditionally tested on content shared online [8, 11, 25]. This disparity in performance highlights the need for a systematic study of the factors influencing AID robustness in real-world settings. Through our analysis, we identify four factors that significantly affect the performance of detectors in the wild:

- (1) **Training data:** In AID, the challenge lies in ensuring that the training data reflects the diversity and complexity of real-world cases. If the training distribution $\mathcal{P}_{\text{train}}(x)$ is derived

from controlled and limited generators, it may diverge from the actual distribution encountered at deployment $\mathcal{P}_{\text{actual}}(x)$.

- (2) **Pre-trained latent space:** A backbone maps input images x to a latent space through a function $\mathcal{B}(x)$, to extract discriminative features that expose generative artifacts [2]. Its effectiveness can be quantified by the expected classification loss $L_{\mathcal{B}} = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim \mathcal{P}_{\text{actual}}} [\ell(G(\mathcal{B}(x)), y)]$ where ℓ is a classification loss function, G is a projection function mapping features to the decision space and y is the true label. Lower $L_{\mathcal{B}}$ implies a more effective backbone for modeling $\mathcal{P}_{\text{actual}}$.
- (3) **Pre-processing methods:** These play a crucial role in ensuring that models can handle input data efficiently, as popular computer vision models, like convolutional neural networks [31] and vision transformers [16], scale quadratically with image size. Instead of the typical 224×224 image size, images in the wild can be several megapixels large. With resizing being considered detrimental for AID—due to its tendency to erase subtle high-frequency traces left by the generation process—cropping techniques become essential [26, 29]. By cropping images into smaller parts through a function $\mathcal{C}(x)$, models can analyze the parts individually and focus on localized details that may carry important information about the presence of synthesis artifacts.
- (4) **Data augmentations:** These are crucial for improving model robustness, as they simulate real-world variations. Data augmentations can be seen as a set of transformations \mathcal{T} applied to the training images, where each transformation $t \in \mathcal{T}$ maps an image $x \sim \mathcal{P}_{\text{train}}(x)$ to a new image $t(x)$. By introducing perturbations similar to those encountered online, the model is exposed to a wider range of potential inputs, improving its generalization capabilities.

Our study systematically evaluates these components to identify optimal strategies for improving AID robustness in the wild. In particular, each of these factors contribute to the overall expected error in AID, which can be expressed as $\epsilon_{\text{AID}} = g(\mathcal{P}_{\text{train}}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{T})$, where g is a function that models their interactions. Our work aims to provide insights regarding such interactions. To facilitate a realistic evaluation setup and address gaps in existing resources, we introduce **ITW-SM**, a new in-the-wild test dataset of 10,000 real and generated images collected from popular social media platforms. Using ITW-SM in tandem with established benchmarks, we provide actionable insights into why current methods fail in the wild and how to improve them. Our contributions include:

- A systematic experimental evaluation revealing the strengths and weaknesses of various AID approaches in the wild.
- The introduction of **ITW-SM**, a new in-the-wild AID benchmark dataset collected from four popular social media platforms, designed to support evaluation under realistic and unconstrained conditions.
- An impact analysis of training data, pre-trained latent spaces, model architectures, pre-processing stages and data augmentations on AID performance in the wild.
- An average improvement of 26.87% in AUC across four types of detectors and under real-world conditions.
- A set of recommendations for designing more robust AID models capable of handling in-the-wild variations.

2 Related Work

AID methods can be categorized in five core categories: end-to-end supervised, vision language (VL) model-based, heuristic, reconstruction and zero-shot approaches.

End-to-end supervised models are trained on labeled datasets, allowing them to learn features that distinguish among real and generated images through supervised learning techniques. Wang et al. [56] fine-tune a pre-trained ResNet50 [21] on 20 different object classes of real images from LSUN [59] and ProGAN [27] images. To better capture generative artifacts, some methods focus on local image patches [3] or combine local and global feature analysis [23]. Another approach avoids downsampling in the early network layers to better preserve generative inconsistencies [20]. Building on this, Corvi et al. [9] fuse networks trained separately on GAN- and diffusion-based images to enhance generalization.

Vision-language approaches effectively distinguish images using features from models like CLIP [45]. Ojha et al. [42] adapt the protocol of [56] by using CLIP as a feature extractor rather than training a ResNet50. Other works improve text-to-image diffusion detection by integrating captions for joint analysis via CLIP’s multimodal embeddings [50], or by extracting representations from both intermediate and final encoder layers (RINE) [30].

Heuristic methods exploit predefined rules and known structural discrepancies between real and synthetic images. LGrad [52] uses gradients from pre-trained CNNs as artifact representations, while Tan et al. [51] detect synthetic content by analyzing neighboring pixel dependencies introduced by upsampling in GANs and VAEs. More recently, AIDE [58] classifies images by combining low-level texture statistics with high-level semantic embeddings.

Reconstruction approaches compare original and reconstructed image variants to highlight areas with artifacts that deviate from a learned distribution. To this end, DIRE [57] measures the discrepancy between an input image and its reconstructed version generated by a pre-trained ablated diffusion model [14], utilizing these differences to train a ResNet50 classifier. In contrast, AER-OBLADE [46] avoids classifier training and directly uses reconstruction errors from a latent diffusion model’s autoencoder, noting that generated images are reconstructed more accurately. Recently, SPAI [26] introduced a spectral detection method to learn the spectral distribution of real images in a self-supervised manner and identify generation artifacts via reconstruction similarity.

Zero-shot approaches detect generated images without being explicitly trained on such content. Early methods in this category model real image distributions via embedding perturbations [22] or pixel-wise reconstruction errors [12]. More recently, vision-language models (VLMs) formulate detection as a multimodal reasoning or visual question answering task. Advanced techniques, including forensically-guided instructions and chain-of-thought reasoning, significantly boost zero-shot accuracy [18, 24], while soft prompt-tuning [4, 28] adapts VLMs for unified detection and source attribution. Despite these advances, recent evaluations reveal that VLMs’ zero-shot performance consistently degrades over time against rapidly evolving generative models [7]. Furthermore, adapting such massive networks to continuous online distribution shifts incurs prohibitive computational costs.

Figure 1: Real (a-e) and generated (f-j) images from our introduced ITW-SM dataset.

While the above works have significantly advanced the field of AID, a growing body of research has also investigated the robustness of AID methods to various perturbations [8, 9, 48] and generative conditions beyond text [19, 40, 41]. These studies often reveal a significant drop in detection accuracy when models trained on unprocessed generated data are evaluated on generated images altered throughout their online lifecycle [25]. This suggests that learned features often overfit to specific generation artifacts and struggle against real-world distortions. To address this, our study sheds light on how common detector design choices interact with the diverse degradations encountered on social media platforms.

Recognizing the domain gap between lab-generated and in-the-wild content, recent datasets source images directly from online platforms. For example, Chameleon [58] curates highly realistic, artist-refined images, but its focus on high-quality art fails to capture the degradation and noise typical of social media posts. TWIGMA [5] provides a large-scale collection of Twitter-scraped AI images, yet it is restricted to a single platform and lacks a balanced collection of authentic images. Broader benchmarks like AIGIBench [60] include social media samples to test robustness against distribution shifts but often lack semantic analysis and any provenance information. To facilitate realistic evaluation, we introduce a balanced, curated dataset sourced directly from verified pages across major social media platforms, including both authentic and AI-generated images.

3 Methodology

We propose an experimental framework (Fig. 2) to systematically evaluate four key components: a) training data composition, b) backbone architecture, c) pre-processing cropping strategy, and d) training data augmentations.

3.1 Training Data Composition

Dataset composition significantly impacts AID robustness. While many studies rely on images from controlled environments or limited generators, such datasets fail to reflect real-world media complexity. Diverse training sets – across both generative models and semantics – enhance generalization to unseen architectures [9, 56], though these benefits eventually level off [25]. Additionally, maintaining a balanced distribution of real and synthetic images is crucial for preventing biases that could hinder generalization. By training on datasets encompassing both benchmark and in-the-wild data, we assess how diversity influences generalization.

3.2 Backbone Architectures for AID

The backbone of a model dictates its ability to extract expressive features and detect subtle synthetic artifacts. Traditional convolutional neural networks (CNNs), such as ResNet [21] and EfficientNet [53], are widely used [9, 10, 15, 20, 23, 39] for their strong spatial feature extraction. Recently, foundational models like CLIP [45] have been adopted [1, 11, 30, 42] for their superior capacity to capture both low-level details and high-level semantics. We evaluate how effectively these architectures identify artifacts and generalize in the wild, including images of varied depicted topics, lighting, resolution, and post-processing.

3.3 Cropping Strategies

Cropping directs models to particular image regions without relying on resizing, which risks erasing subtle high-frequency generation traces via interpolation [9]. While center and random cropping remain the most common approaches, alternatives like 10-cropping (evaluating the center, four corners, and horizontal flips) have been utilized during inference to enhance performance [30]. Additionally, texture-based cropping [29] targets high-frequency regions (e.g.,

Figure 2: Framework for studying the factors impacting expected performance and generalization in AID models.

Table 1: Comparison between the proposed ITW-SM dataset and existing in the wild datasets.

Key Differentiating Characteristics	ITW-SM	Chameleon	TWIGMA
AI-generated Images Source	Social media users	AI-painting communities	Twitter users
Real Images Source	Verified social media accounts	Unsplash (photographers)	-
Number of Social Media Platforms	4	0	1
Resolution Range (All Images)	0.1 - 45 Megapixels	0.1 - 31 Megapixels	< 0.01 - 47 Megapixels
Size	10,000	26,033	800,000
Intended Evaluation Focus	General in-the-wild robustness	Generalization to realistic AI	Analysis of AI art trends

Figure 3: Topic distribution in web-collected datasets.

edges, fine textures), demonstrating superiority over resizing and previous cropping methods. We systematically evaluate each strategy under a consistent pipeline to isolate its impact on detection performance.

3.4 Data Augmentations

Data augmentations simulate real-world distortions to improve model generalization. Common AID augmentations include compression (e.g., JPEG, WebP) to mimic online sharing artifacts, geometric transformations (cropping, rotating, flipping) for framing robustness, and noise/filtering techniques (Gaussian noise, blurring,

Figure 4: Resolution distribution in web-collected datasets.

sharpening) to build resilience against post-processing. Building on prior findings linking augmentation to detector robustness [39, 56], we investigate whether these augmentations enhance robustness when evaluated on heavily processed images.

4 ITW-SM Dataset

To meet the needs of our evaluation, we introduce the **In The Wild - Social Media Dataset (ITW-SM)**, specifically designed to reflect the complexity and diversity of online media content.

4.1 Dataset Composition

The ITW-SM dataset comprises **10,000 images**, evenly split between real and AI-generated ones. Real images are collected from verified, trusted accounts across four popular platforms: Facebook,

Instagram, LinkedIn, and X. These were chosen to represent a diverse range of online content and image characteristics. Highlighting the real-world diversity, the images cover a wide range of topics and resolutions. Synthetic images are sourced from public accounts known to consistently share AI-generated content, including artists and communities that openly post images created with such tools. A comparison with previously introduced datasets that were also sampled from the web is presented in Table 1.

4.2 Collection Procedure

Data collection was performed using a custom crawler that respects the terms of service of each platform. For each platform real content was scraped from verified accounts to ensure authenticity. AI-generated content was scraped from user accounts and community pages dedicated to sharing AI-generated visuals. All images were saved in their original resolution, preserving native compression artifacts. A multi-stage filtering pipeline was employed to ensure quality and consistency. First, images with heavy text overlays, watermarks, or non-photographic content (e.g., memes, screenshots) were removed. Then duplicates were eliminated using similarity scores and all samples were manually reviewed to verify label correctness. Moreover, as we wanted to maintain the distribution of AI-generated content shared online, and not merely make a dataset difficult to human evaluators, we avoided discarding images whose semantics may help to reveal whether they are generated or not. Fig. 1 illustrates some indicative samples of ITW-SM.

To better understand the composition of ITW-SM, we compare its topic and resolution distributions against existing web-sampled datasets, like Chameleon. For topic analysis, we define a taxonomy of 14 broad semantic categories (e.g., People, Nature, Art, Text/Memes) and perform zero-shot classification using OpenCLIP ViT-B/32 [6], assigning images based on maximum text-image cosine similarity. As Fig. 3 illustrates, topic distributions differ significantly between social media platforms and online painting communities. Additionally, ITW-SM exhibits a substantially broader resolution range, particularly for real images (Fig. 4).

5 Experimental Setup

5.1 Datasets

We train our detection models using both lab-controlled and in-the-wild data. For lab-controlled data, we use the LDM Training Dataset [9], a widely adopted benchmark that represents the architectural baseline for modern latent diffusion models [47]. For in-the-wild data, we utilize TWIGMA [5], a large-scale collection of web-sourced AI-generated images, combined with an equal number of real images from OpenImages [32]. This combination provides a robust foundation for evaluating generalization without over-fitting to the absolute newest generative architectures.

To bridge the gap between controlled experiments and real-world scenarios, we evaluate the models on three distinct datasets: Synthbuster [2], a highly-controlled benchmark containing 9k images generated by 9 models and 1k uncompressed real images from RAISE [13]; Chameleon [58], an in-the-wild dataset comprising over 11k high-fidelity AI and 14k real images from online creative communities; and our novel ITW-SM dataset, curated from four social media platforms to capture a diverse, real-world image distribution.

5.2 AID Models

For our experiments, we utilize one representative model from each of the main categories in Section 2 (end-to-end supervised, VL model-based, heuristic, reconstruction and zero-shot).

- **DMID** [9] fuses the logits of two ResNet50 models independently trained on GAN- and diffusion-generated images. Both models utilize intense data augmentation and avoid down-sampling in their first layers.
- **RINE** [30] leverages representations from intermediate CLIP Transformer blocks [45] to capture both fine-grained details and high-level semantics. A trainable weighting module determines block importance, and a lightweight network maps features into a forgery-aware vector space.
- **NPR** [51] detects artifacts introduced by generative up-scaling layers. It utilizes neighboring pixel relationships to train a detector focusing on the local pixel interdependencies caused by these up-sampling operators.
- **SPAI** [26] learns the real image distribution via masked spectral learning and frequency reconstruction. It detects out-of-distribution generated images using spectral reconstruction similarity, and employs spectral context attention to capture subtle inconsistencies across varying resolutions.
- **Gemma 3 IT 27B** [54] is a zero-shot method that treats detection as a visual question-answering task as in [7]. Employed prompts constrain the output to strictly “AI” or “REAL”. To ensure deterministic, single-token responses, we apply a 0.1 temperature and a 32-token maximum output.

5.3 Evaluation Protocol

To ensure a fair comparison of different AID methods, we retrain each model following the training details provided in their respective papers. In total, our experiments required more than 1000 GPU hours. While we adhere to the original training strategies of each detection approach, we make controlled adjustments to the backbones (when applicable), datasets, preprocessing methods, and augmentations to align with our experimental setup. To ensure computational feasibility across all methods, we apply similar resource constraints during training.

6 Results

Our findings confirm a key limitation previously discussed: while most methods achieve strong results on curated benchmark datasets, their performance degrades significantly when applied to in-the-wild AI-generated images, as illustrated in Fig. 5. To better understand the impact of each component in isolation, we vary one factor at a time while keeping the others fixed. We then compare the results from the original implementations, as reported in the respective papers, with those obtained through our re-evaluation.

6.1 Backbone

Recognizing the significance of selecting effective backbones for AID tasks, we conducted an ablation study centered on the CLIP-based RINE model trained on LDM data. We selected RINE because it exemplifies a representative, simple and competitive approach in the recent literature of AID methods. In our study, we replaced the CLIP L/14 backbone [45] in RINE with various alternative vision

Figure 5: Detection performance (AUC) on benchmark data (*Academic*), as reported in original papers, and in the wild (*ITW*).

Table 2: Performance (AUC/AP) of RINE with different backbones. Remaining components fixed to “LDM+TWIGMA (1.2M)”, “Texture cropping”, “With augmentations”. For each training configuration, we explore a hyperparameter grid to achieve optimal performance, where ξ is the contrastive loss factor, q denotes the index of the network’s layer, d is the output dimensionality of the backbone and d' the output dimensionality of the projected feature space. Best values are highlighted in bold.

Model	Training Data	Hyperparameters				Detection Performance (AUC / AP)			
		ξ	q	d	d'	Synthbuster	Chameleon	ITW-SM	Average
CLIP L/14 [45]	400M	0.2	2	1024	1024	96.98 / 97.33	82.25 / 81.34	96.53 / 96.98	91.92 / 91.88
OpenCLIP L/14 [6]	2B	0.2	2	1024	128	74.82 / 81.11	85.86 / 83.03	90.01 / 91.54	83.56 / 85.23
CLIP H/14 [6]	2B	0.1	4	1280	256	97.02 / 81.71	81.22 / 76.98	90.56 / 91.81	89.60 / 83.50
BLIP2 [33]	129M	0.2	1	1408	1408	99.37 / 99.48	86.58 / 86.28	96.49 / 96.97	94.15 / 94.24
DINO-V2-L/14 [43]	142M	0.8	1	1024	512	99.14 / 99.18	87.33 / 85.51	98.23 / 98.50	94.90 / 94.40

Table 3: Training data configurations.

Dataset	LDM Subset		TWIGMA Subset	
	Real	Gen.	Real	Gen.
LDM	200K	200K	-	-
TWIGMA	-	-	600K	600K
LDM+TWIGMA (400K)	200K	200K	200K	200K
LDM+TWIGMA (1.2M)	200K	200K	600K	600K

encoders. The backbone is characterized by three main components: the architecture itself, the pretraining objective, and the dataset used during pretraining. In this ablation, we primarily focus on Vision Transformer (ViT)-based architectures, so the key variations lie in the pretraining objectives and the diversity of the pretraining datasets. The encoders tested include:

- **OpenCLIP L/14** [6]: This open-source implementation of CLIP is designed to provide greater flexibility and transparency in large-scale VL modeling. OpenCLIP L/14 is trained on the LAION-2B dataset [49] and also extends the CLIP architecture with improvements in training.
- **BLIP2** [33]: This integrates frozen pre-trained image encoders with large language models (LLMs) by employing a lightweight 12-layer Transformer encoder in between, trained on a 129M image dataset introduced in [34], achieving state-of-the-art results on various VL tasks.
- **CLIP H/14** [6]: This variant of the CLIP model employs advanced scaling techniques to enhance performance across different applications. It is a larger and more powerful version of CLIP L/14 trained also on LAION-2B [49].
- **DINO-V2-L/14** [43]: This is pretrained on large curated datasets without supervision. It incorporates an optimized training recipe, increased model scale, and a larger curated

dataset, LVD-142M [43], along with a distillation process that enables smaller models to benefit from the capabilities of the most powerful ViT architecture.

We present the respective performance in Table 2. DINO-V2’s superior performance likely stems from its self-supervised training focused purely on visual understanding, its ability to capture both low-level and semantic features robustly, and the scale and curation of its training data. Results further highlight the importance of quality pre-training data. One additional explanation is that CLIP-based methods’ reliance on image-text alignment may introduce semantic shortcuts, emphasizing contextual relevance over fine-grained visual details. This can lead to representations that are less sensitive to low-level inconsistencies—such as texture aberrations or local artifacts—that are crucial for detecting AI-generated content and should be jointly considered with image semantics.

6.2 Training Data

We use the LDM training dataset [9] and TWIGMA [5] to retrain our models. The former consists of 200K latent diffusion-generated images and 200K real images sourced from two public datasets: MS COCO [37] and LSUN [59]. All images in this dataset are of low resolution. We consider 600K AI-generated images from TWIGMA for training, while we use an equal number of real images from the OpenImages dataset [32]. This includes both low- and high-resolution images. We combine these datasets to create four training datasets, as can be seen in Table 3.

Based on our analysis in Table 4, we first observe that the performance of all detection approaches benefits from training on data collected in the wild, even when considering lab-generated benchmarks, like Synthbuster. However, approaches that heavily rely on pre-trained spaces, like RINE and SPAI, are only marginally affected by increasing the training data scale. Instead, the performance of

Table 4: Performance (AUC/AP) of detection methods when trained on different data configurations. Rest components fixed to “DINO-V2-L/14”, “Texture cropping”, “With augmentations”. Best values per approach are highlighted in bold.

	Synthbuster	Chameleon	ITW-SM	Average
NPR				
LDM	55.95 / 58.47	53.04 / 44.57	54.85 / 55.92	54.61 / 52.99
TWIGMA	69.79 / 71.67	60.54 / 53.96	80.00 / 81.63	70.11 / 69.09
LDM+TWIGMA (400K)	63.51 / 66.56	63.29 / 55.77	43.59 / 52.66	56.80 / 58.33
LDM+TWIGMA (1.2M)	71.31 / 74.86	56.29 / 49.89	77.54 / 77.73	68.38 / 67.49
Gemma 3 IT 27B				
zero-shot	70.61 / 70.54	85.01 / 79.56	84.04 / 75.50	79.89 / 75.20
DMID				
LDM	81.26 / 82.79	54.69 / 55.03	79.96 / 81.87	71.97 / 73.23
TWIGMA	90.27 / 90.15	82.97 / 78.51	91.55 / 92.03	88.26 / 86.90
LDM+TWIGMA (400K)	89.23 / 89.2	77.81 / 72.85	88.04 / 85.95	85.03 / 82.67
LDM+TWIGMA (1.2M)	92.4 / 91.65	83.71 / 79.33	92.26 / 92.58	89.46 / 87.85
RINE				
LDM	95.04 / 95.39	63.94 / 52.79	83.52 / 83.07	80.83 / 77.08
TWIGMA	97.77 / 97.96	89.03 / 86.69	97.66 / 98.07	94.82 / 94.24
LDM+TWIGMA (400K)	99.61 / 99.66	86.51 / 85.12	97.90 / 98.20	94.67 / 94.33
LDM+TWIGMA (1.2M)	99.14 / 99.18	87.33 / 85.51	98.23 / 98.50	94.90 / 94.40
SPAI				
LDM	93.87 / 94.17	72.28 / 61.28	78.93 / 80.17	81.69 / 78.54
TWIGMA	-	-	-	-
LDM+TWIGMA (400K)	98.81 / 99.02	89.38 / 87.26	97.59 / 97.80	95.26 / 94.69
LDM+TWIGMA (1.2M)	97.45 / 98.00	90.21 / 88.51	98.10 / 98.35	95.25 / 94.95

Table 5: Performance (AUC/AP) of detection methods when trained using different cropping methods. Rest components fixed to “DINO-V2-L/14”, “LDM+TWIGMA (1.2M)”, “With augmentations”. Best values per approach are highlighted in bold.

	Synthbuster	Chameleon	ITW-SM	Average
DMID				
Center cropping	89.41 / 89.58	63.2 / 58.98	83.74 / 80.06	78.78 / 76.21
Texture cropping	92.4 / 91.65	83.71 / 79.33	92.26 / 95.58	89.46 / 87.85
RINE				
Center cropping	94.65 / 94.65	84.08 / 82.7	95.04 / 95.75	91.26 / 91.03
Texture cropping	99.14 / 99.18	87.33 / 85.51	98.23 / 98.50	94.90 / 94.40
NPR				
Center cropping	69.79 / 71.67	60.54 / 53.96	80.00 / 81.63	70.11 / 69.09
Texture cropping	64.08 / 65.78	62.34 / 54.24	76.03 / 76.98	67.48 / 65.67

Figure 6: Original and updated model performance (AUC).

Table 6: Performance (AUC/AP) of detection methods, trained on “LDM+TWIGMA (1.2M)” dataset, using different augmentations. Rest components fixed to “DINO-V2-L/14”, “Texture cropping”. Best values per approach are highlighted in bold.

	Synthbuster	Chameleon	ITW-SM	Average
DMID				
Without augmentations	76.53 / 66.47	76.21 / 69.36	82.20 / 81.42	78.31 / 72.42
With augmentations	92.4 / 91.65	83.71 / 79.33	92.26 / 92.58	89.46 / 87.85
RINE				
Without augmentations	93.63 / 95.02	92.16 / 90.24	93.70 / 94.03	93.16 / 93.10
With augmentations	99.14 / 99.18	87.33 / 85.51	98.23 / 98.50	94.90 / 94.40
NPR				
Without augmentations	72.35 / 69.61	60.80 / 48.49	68.92 / 64.09	67.36 / 60.73
With augmentations	64.08 / 65.78	62.34 / 54.24	76.03 / 76.98	67.48 / 65.67
SPAI				
Without augmentations	94.80 / 94.83	82.73 / 81.02	91.46 / 91.75	89.66 / 89.20
With augmentations	97.45 / 98.00	90.21 / 88.51	98.10 / 98.35	95.25 / 94.95

the end-to-end supervised detector DMID, due to optimizing all its representations from scratch, benefits significantly more from such a scaling. Also, targeting specific generation artifacts, like in the case of NPR, significantly prevents an approach to benefit from more diverse training data.

6.3 Cropping Method

Inspired by the promising results of [29], we adopt TextureCrop during training, randomly selecting one of the 10 crops per image to reduce overhead. It is important to note that the SPAI model is not included in this analysis, as it natively operates on patches of the original image rather than a single crop.

Based on our results, TextureCrop appears to significantly boost performance compared to center cropping on the DMID and RINE methods, as it enables them to process more informative image and capture more robust generation traces, by targeting regions with high texture information. However, advanced cropping approaches can also compromise the ability of detectors that make strong assumptions about the generative artifacts. This is exemplified by NPR, of which the performance degrades when altering the expected cropping format.

6.4 Augmentations

By artificially expanding the diversity of the training set, augmentation techniques help the model recognize generative artifacts across varying conditions and scenarios. Our experimental results demonstrate that incorporating comprehensive data augmentation strategies improves on average the performance metrics (AUC/AP) of all methods across all three datasets, as seen in Table 6. Interestingly, for RINE, augmentations slightly degrade performance on Chameleon, suggesting that the applied augmentations may have introduced transformations that deviate from the types of distortions found in the dataset. For most methods, we used the augmentations mentioned in the corresponding papers. However,

for the NPR model, since no intense augmentations were originally applied, we considered the augmentation pipeline of [30].

6.5 Comparison of Original and Updated Implementations

To assess the impact of our proposed modifications, we compare the performance of the original implementations and the updated models after applying our changes. The obtained results are presented in Fig. 6, where we display the AUC values for each method before and after applying our updates. Our modifications yield significant improvements in AID performance, which attests to their efficacy, especially for tackling AID in the wild.

7 Conclusion

Our study highlights the critical challenges that AID models face in real-world applications and identifies key factors that influence detection performance. By analyzing the role of backbone architectures, training data composition, cropping methods, and data augmentations, we provide actionable insights for improving AID robustness. The findings demonstrate the need for more robust detection techniques that account for real-world variations and remain effective in practical settings. Such analysis should be conducted on any new model to be deployed in the wild, as different models exhibit different behaviors and may require tailored strategies for optimal performance.

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References

- [1] Roberto Amoroso, Davide Morelli, Marcella Cornia, Lorenzo Baraldi, Alberto Del Bimbo, and Rita Cucchiara. 2024. Parents and children: Distinguishing multimodal deepfakes from natural images. *ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing, Communications and Applications* 21, 1 (2024), 1–23.
- [2] Quentin Bamme. 2023. Synthbuster: Towards Detection of Diffusion Model Generated Images. In *IEEE Open Journal of Signal Processing*.
- [3] Lucy Chai, David Bau, Ser-Nam Lim, and Phillip Isola. 2020. What makes fake images detectable? understanding properties that generalize. In *European conference on computer vision*. Springer, 103–120.
- [4] Chu-Fu Chang et al. 2025. AntifakePrompt: Prompt-Tuned Vision-Language Models are Fake Image Detectors. In *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*.
- [5] Yiqun Chen and James Y Zou. 2023. Twigma: A dataset of ai-generated images with metadata from twitter. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 36 (2023), 37748–37760.
- [6] Mehdi Cherti, Romain Beaumont, Ross Wightman, Mitchell Wortsman, Gabriel Ilharco, Cade Gordon, Christoph Schuhmann, Ludwig Schmidt, and Jenia Jitsev. 2023. Reproducible Scaling Laws for Contrastive Language-Image Learning. In *2023 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*. IEEE, 2818–2829. doi:10.1109/cvpr52729.2023.00276
- [7] Zacharias Chrysidis, Stefanos-Iordanis Papadopoulos, and Symeon Papadopoulos. 2026. The Synthetic Media Shift: Tracking the Rise, Virality, and Detectability of AI-Generated Multimodal Misinformation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2604.15372* (2026).
- [8] Riccardo Corvi, Davide Cozzolino, Giovanni Poggi, Koki Nagano, and Luisa Verdoliva. 2023. Intriguing properties of synthetic images: from generative adversarial networks to diffusion models. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 973–982.
- [9] Riccardo Corvi, Davide Cozzolino, Giada Zingarini, Giovanni Poggi, Koki Nagano, and Luisa Verdoliva. 2023. On the detection of synthetic images generated by diffusion models. In *ICASSP 2023-2023 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*. IEEE, 1–5.
- [10] Davide Cozzolino, Diego Gragnaniello, Giovanni Poggi, and Luisa Verdoliva. 2021. Towards universal gan image detection. In *2021 International conference on visual communications and image processing (VCIP)*. IEEE, 1–5.
- [11] Davide Cozzolino, Giovanni Poggi, Riccardo Corvi, Matthias Nießner, and Luisa Verdoliva. 2024. Raising the bar of ai-generated image detection with clip. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 4356–4366.
- [12] Davide Cozzolino, Giovanni Poggi, Matthias Nießner, and Luisa Verdoliva. 2024. Zero-shot detection of ai-generated images. In *European conference on computer vision*. Springer, 54–72.
- [13] Duc-Tien Dang-Nguyen, Cecilia Pasquini, Valentina Conotter, and Giulia Boato. 2015. RAISE: a raw images dataset for digital image forensics. In *Proceedings of the 6th ACM Multimedia Systems Conference*.
- [14] Prafulla Dhariwal and Alexander Nichol. 2021. Diffusion models beat gans on image synthesis. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 34 (2021), 8780–8794.
- [15] Pantelis Dogoulis, Giorgos Kordopatis-Zilos, Ioannis Kompatsiaris, and Symeon Papadopoulos. 2023. Improving Synthetically Generated Image Detection in Cross-Concept Settings. In *Proceedings of the 2nd ACM International Workshop on Multimedia AI against Disinformation (ICMR '23)*. ACM. doi:10.1145/3592572.3592846
- [16] Alexey Dosovitskiy, Lucas Beyer, Alexander Kolesnikov, Dirk Weissenborn, Xiaohua Zhai, Thomas Unterthiner, Mostafa Dehghani, Matthias Minderer, Georg Heigold, Sylvain Gelly, Jakob Uszkoreit, and Neil Houlsby. 2021. An Image is Worth 16x16 Words: Transformers for Image Recognition at Scale. In *International Conference on Learning Representations*.
- [17] Ricard Durall, Margret Keuper, and Janis Keuper. 2020. Watch your upconvolution: Cnn based generative deep neural networks are failing to reproduce spectral distributions. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 7890–7899.
- [18] Leonardo Galteri et al. 2025. Prompt-Engineered Detection of AI-Generated Images. *ResearchGate preprint* (2025).
- [19] Paschalis Giakoumoglou, Dimitrios Karageorgiou, Symeon Papadopoulos, and Panagiotis C Petrantonakis. 2025. SAGI: Semantically Aligned and Uncertainty Guided AI Image Inpainting. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 16090–16101.
- [20] D Gragnaniello, D Cozzolino, F Marra, G Poggi, L Verdoliva, et al. 2021. Are GAN generated images easy to detect? A critical analysis of the state-of-the-art. In *IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo (ICME)*.
- [21] Kaiming He, Xiangyu Zhang, Shaoqing Ren, and Jian Sun. 2016. Deep residual learning for image recognition. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 770–778.
- [22] Zhiyuan He, Pin-Yu Chen, and Tsung-Yi Ho. 2024. RIGID: A Training-free and Model-Agnostic Framework for Robust AI-Generated Image Detection. *arXiv:2405.20112* [cs.CV] <https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.20112>
- [23] Yan Ju, Shan Jia, Lipeng Ke, Hongfei Xue, Koki Nagano, and Siwei Lyu. 2022. Fusing global and local features for generalized ai-synthesized image detection. In *2022 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*. IEEE, 3465–3469.
- [24] Zohar Kachwala, Danishjeet Singh, Daniel Yang, and Filippo Menczer. 2025. Task-aligned prompting improves zero-shot detection of AI-generated images by Vision-Language Models. *arXiv preprint* (2025).
- [25] Dimitrios Karageorgiou, Quentin Bamme, Valentin Porcellini, Bertrand Goupil, Denis Teyssou, and Symeon Papadopoulos. 2024. Evolution of detection performance throughout the online lifespan of synthetic images. In *European Conference on Computer Vision*. Springer, 400–417.
- [26] Dimitrios Karageorgiou, Symeon Papadopoulos, Ioannis Kompatsiaris, and Efstratios Gavves. 2025. Any-resolution ai-generated image detection by spectral learning. In *Proceedings of the Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference*. 18706–18717.
- [27] Tero Karras, Timo Aila, Samuli Laine, and Jaakko Lehtinen. 2018. Progressive Growing of GANs for Improved Quality, Stability, and Variation. In *International Conference on Learning Representations*.
- [28] Mamadou Keita, Wassim Hamidouche, Hessen Bougueffia Eutamene, Abdelmalik Taleb-Ahmed, and Abdenour Hadid. 2024. FIDAVL: Fake Image Detection and Attribution using Vision-Language Model. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2409.03109* (2024).
- [29] Despina Konstantinidou, Christos Koutlis, and Symeon Papadopoulos. 2025. Texturecrop: Enhancing synthetic image detection through texture-based cropping. In *Proceedings of the Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision*. 1459–1468.
- [30] Christos Koutlis and Symeon Papadopoulos. 2024. Leveraging representations from intermediate encoder-blocks for synthetic image detection. In *European Conference on computer vision*. Springer, 394–411.
- [31] Alex Krizhevsky, Ilya Sutskever, and Geoffrey E Hinton. 2012. Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 25 (2012).
- [32] Alina Kuznetsova, Hassan Rom, Neil Alldrin, Jasper Uijlings, Ivan Krasin, Jordi Pont-Tuset, Shahab Kamali, Stefan Popov, Matteo Malloi, Alexander Kolesnikov, et al. 2020. The open images dataset v4: Unified image classification, object detection, and visual relationship detection at scale. *International journal of computer vision* 128, 7 (2020), 1956–1981.
- [33] Junnan Li, Dongxu Li, Silvio Savarese, and Steven Hoi. 2023. BliP-2: Bootstrapping language-image pre-training with frozen image encoders and large language models. In *International conference on machine learning*. PMLR, 19730–19742.
- [34] Junnan Li, Ramprasaath Selvaraju, Akhilesh Gotmare, Shafiq Joty, Caiming Xiong, and Steven Chu Hong Hoi. 2021. Align before fuse: Vision and language representation learning with momentum distillation. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 34 (2021), 9694–9705.
- [35] Jun Li, Chenyang Zhang, Wei Zhu, and Yawei Ren. 2025. A comprehensive survey of image generation models based on deep learning. *Annals of Data Science* 12, 1 (2025), 141–170.
- [36] Yanhao Li, Quentin Bamme, Marina Gardella, Tina Nikoukhah, Jean-Michel Morel, Miguel Colom, and Rafael Grompone Von Gioi. 2024. MaskSim: Detection of Synthetic Images by Masked Spectrum Similarity Analysis. In *2023 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*. IEEE, 3855–3865.
- [37] Tsung-Yi Lin, Michael Maire, Serge Belongie, James Hays, Pietro Perona, Deva Ramanan, Piotr Dollár, and C Lawrence Zitnick. 2014. Microsoft coco: Common objects in context. In *European conference on computer vision*. Springer, 740–755.
- [38] Zeyu Lu, Di Huang, Lei Bai, Jingjing Qu, Chengyue Wu, Xihui Liu, and Wanli Ouyang. 2023. Seeing is not always believing: Benchmarking human and model perception of ai-generated images. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 36 (2023), 25435–25447.
- [39] Sara Mandelli, Nicolò Bonettini, Paolo Bestagini, and Stefano Tubaro. 2022. Detecting gan-generated images by orthogonal training of multiple cnns. In *2022 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*. IEEE, 3091–3095.
- [40] Hannes Mareen, Dimitrios Karageorgiou, Paschalis Giakoumoglou, Peter Lambert, Symeon Papadopoulos, and Glenn Van Wallendael. 2026. TGIF2: extended text-guided inpainting forgery dataset and benchmark. *Journal on Information Security* (2026).
- [41] Hannes Mareen, Dimitrios Karageorgiou, Glenn Van Wallendael, Peter Lambert, and Symeon Papadopoulos. 2024. TGIF: Text-guided inpainting forgery dataset. In *2024 IEEE International Workshop on Information Forensics and Security (WIFS)*. IEEE, 1–6.
- [42] Utkarsh Ojha, Yuheng Li, and Yong Jae Lee. 2023. Towards universal fake image detectors that generalize across generative models. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 24480–24489.
- [43] Maxime Oquab, Timothée Darcet, Théo Moutakanni, Huy Vo, Marc Szafraniec, Vasil Khalidov, Pierre Fernandez, Daniel Haziza, Francisco Massa, Alaaeldin El-Nouby, Mahmoud Assran, Nicolas Ballas, Wojciech Galuba, Russell Howes, Po-Yao Huang, Shang-Wen Li, Ishan Misra, Michael Rabbat, Vasu Sharma, Gabriel Synnaeve, Hu Xu, Hervé Jegou, Julien Mairal, Patrick Labatut, Armand Joulin, and Piotr Bojanowski. 2024. DINOv2: Learning Robust Visual Features without Supervision. *Transactions on Machine Learning Research Journal* (2024).

- [44] L. Papa, L. Faiella, L. Corvitto, L. Maiano, and I. Amerini. 2023. On the use of Stable Diffusion for creating realistic faces: From generation to detection.. In *11th International Workshop on Biometrics and Forensics (IWBF)*. 1–6.
- [45] Alec Radford, Jong Wook Kim, Chris Hallacy, Aditya Ramesh, Gabriel Goh, Sandhini Agarwal, Girish Sastry, Amanda Askell, Pamela Mishkin, Jack Clark, et al. 2021. Learning transferable visual models from natural language supervision. In *International conference on machine learning*. PmlR, 8748–8763.
- [46] Jonas Ricker, Denis Lukovnikov, and Asja Fischer. 2024. Aeroblade: Training-free detection of latent diffusion images using autoencoder reconstruction error. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 9130–9140.
- [47] Robin Rombach, Andreas Blattmann, Dominik Lorenz, Patrick Esser, and Björn Ommer. 2022. High-resolution image synthesis with latent diffusion models. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 10684–10695.
- [48] Manos Schinas and Symeon Papadopoulos. 2024. SIDBench: A Python framework for reliably assessing synthetic image detection methods. In *Proceedings of the 3rd ACM International Workshop on Multimedia AI against Disinformation*. 55–64.
- [49] Christoph Schuhmann, Romain Beaumont, Richard Vencu, Cade Gordon, Ross Wightman, Mehdi Cherti, Theo Coombes, Aarush Katta, Clayton Mullis, Mitchell Wortsman, Patrick Schramowski, Srivatsa Kundurthy, Katherine Crowson, Ludwig Schmidt, Robert Kaczmarczyk, and Jenia Jitsev. 2022. Laion-5b: An open large-scale dataset for training next generation image-text models. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 35 (2022), 25278–25294.
- [50] Zeyang Sha, Zheng Li, Ning Yu, and Yang Zhang. 2023. De-fake: Detection and attribution of fake images generated by text-to-image generation models. In *Proceedings of the 2023 ACM SIGSAC conference on computer and communications security*. 3418–3432.
- [51] Chuangchuang Tan, Yao Zhao, Shikui Wei, Guanghua Gu, Ping Liu, and Yunchao Wei. 2024. Rethinking the up-sampling operations in cnn-based generative network for generalizable deepfake detection. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 28130–28139.
- [52] Chuangchuang Tan, Yao Zhao, Shikui Wei, Guanghua Gu, and Yunchao Wei. 2023. Learning on Gradients: Generalized Artifacts Representation for GAN-Generated Images Detection. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 12105–12114.
- [53] Mingxing Tan and Quoc Le. 2019. Efficientnet: Rethinking model scaling for convolutional neural networks. In *International conference on machine learning*. PMLR, 6105–6114.
- [54] Gemma Team. 2025. Gemma 3 Technical Report. arXiv:2503.19786 [cs.CL] <https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.19786>
- [55] Luke Tredinnick and Claire Laybats. 2023. The dangers of generative artificial intelligence. 46–48 pages.
- [56] Sheng-Yu Wang, Oliver Wang, Richard Zhang, Andrew Owens, and Alexei A Efros. 2020. CNN-generated images are surprisingly easy to spot... for now. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 8695–8704.
- [57] Zhendong Wang, Jianmin Bao, Wengang Zhou, Weilun Wang, Hezhen Hu, Hong Chen, and Houqiang Li. 2023. Dire for diffusion-generated image detection. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 22445–22455.
- [58] Shilin Yan, Ouxiang Li, Jiayin Cai, Yanbin Hao, Xiaolong Jiang, Yao Hu, and Weidi Xie. 2025. A Sanity Check for AI-generated Image Detection. In *International Conference on Learning Representations*.
- [59] Fisher Yu, Ari Seff, Yinda Zhang, Shuran Song, Thomas Funkhouser, and Jianxiong Xiao. 2016. LSUN: Construction of a Large-scale Image Dataset using Deep Learning with Humans in the Loop. arXiv:1506.03365 [cs.CV] <https://arxiv.org/abs/1506.03365>
- [60] Kai Zeng et al. 2025. Is Artificial Intelligence Generated Image Detection a Solved Problem?. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, Vol. 38. <https://openreview.net/forum?id=N52U2h9k9o>